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Development of NutriKropeck: An Innovative *Malunggay* and Scallop Functional Marine-Based Snack with Student-Friendly Pricing

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Abstract

Objective: To develop and evaluate NutriKropeck, an innovative *malunggay* (*Moringa oleifera*) and scallop-enriched kropeck, and determine its potential as a functional, affordable, and nutritious marine-based snack for learners. **Method:** This study used an experimental research design to assess the acceptability of the products, the logo, and pricing. 35 panelists were selected to help the researcher evaluate the *malunggay*-scallop kropeck. The sensory evaluation used was aroma, taste, color, texture, and general acceptability. To analyze the data, statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and ANOVA were used. **Findings:** Treatment D was Extremely Acceptable in all categories, like aroma, color, taste, texture, and general acceptability, compared to Treatment A, B, and C. The formulation of Treatment D was very consistent with the panelists' liking. In terms of logo, Logo 3 got the highest percentage of 74, compared to Logo 1 and Logo 2. While the price is very affordable, 40 grams is P25.00, and 50 grams is P35.00 pesos. There were no significant differences among the categories of aroma, color, taste, texture, and general acceptability. **Novelty:** This study introduces about the great potential of providing a nutritional snack to Filipino children by combining *Malunggay* and Scallops. But Further studies were recommended, such as nutritional values, shelf life, and packaging. Also, collaboration from various stakeholders, from local government units to national agencies and academe, really plays a pivotal role in achieving the elevated potential of this research paper. Financial support for a start-up business serving the local community in Northern Iloilo is also needed to sustain the product.

Keywords: Functional Snack; *Malunggay*; Scallop; NutriKropeck; Sensory Evaluation; Filipino Children

1 Introduction

In the Philippines, malnutrition and limited access to affordable, nutritious snacks remain a perennial problem in the Department of Education. In response, many educators, researchers, and experts in food innovation have been exploring the development of functional foods enhanced with health-promoting ingredients that provide nutritional value beyond basic sustenance. Recent advancements in food science highlight the integration of locally available agricultural products, both on land and at sea, to create nutrient-dense, economical snack alternatives suitable for community and school settings.

Malunggay is highly recognized for its high vitamin A and C content, calcium and iron, and antioxidant content. *Malunggay* has gained recognition for its potential health benefits, such as reducing inflammation and supporting metabolic health⁽¹⁾. Beyond nutrition, *malunggay* is also used as a traditional medicine. In general, the tree can withstand harsh conditions, making this crop a source of food security and livelihood support. Specifically, this study will utilize *malunggay* leaves, which offer significant nutritional benefits.

Malunggay is used in bakery and meat products due to its high levels of polyphenols, bioactive peptides, carotenoids, and glucosinolates⁽²⁾. Furthermore, another study was conducted to formulate a cereal enhanced with *malunggay* leaves; formula 4 was the one recommended by the evaluators. However, further study is recommended to meet the Indonesian National Standard (SNI) for crude fiber, water, and fat⁽³⁾. Also, adding *malunggay* to bread, pastries, and even beverages increase the nutritional profile of the products. Dried leaves can also provide the same protein as eggs and milk⁽⁴⁾. But one study found that a common problem with using *malunggay* is the availability of fresh, high-quality resources. But with the help of the national government, to address this gap. Certain policies must be improved to encourage local farmers to concentrate on *malunggay* farming to improve the quality of *malunggay* products, such as leaves and seeds⁽⁵⁾. According to one study, *malunggay* is widely promoted as a promising plant for combating malnutrition⁽⁶⁾. This has been the Department of Education (DepEd)'s advocacy for decades: improving health and providing learners with food to enhance academic performance.

Scallops (*Pecten spp.*), on the other hand, are an excellent source of lean proteins, omega-3 fatty acids, and essential minerals for cardiovascular health and well-being. They are also rich in vitamin B12, magnesium, phosphorus, and zinc, which support metabolism, nerve function, and immune function⁽⁷⁾. Scallops also have a pleasant taste, but they vary with the season. Summer and spring scallops have a superior taste, but winter scallops have healthier unsaturated fatty acids and richer fat-soluble vitamins⁽⁸⁾. Thus, scallops have potential for food product development. If fish and shrimp are ingredients for kropecks, scallops can also be an alternative. But when the scallop meat dried, a distinct umami perception was very evident. This is the fifth taste, a savory, both-meaty taste⁽⁹⁾.

In a restaurant, scallops are considered expensive; they are the main ingredient for the chef's special. For local delicacies, Hokkaido-dried scallops are famous among tourists, often as homecoming gifts. As an ingredient in kropeck, this helps increase protein density while maintaining low fat and calorie levels. One study on kropeck scallops found that all formulations were very acceptable in terms of aroma, flavor, color, texture, and overall acceptability. This study also found no significant differences in acceptability across all categories⁽¹⁰⁾.

This research paper focuses on producing NutriKropeck as a nutritional snack for children. The main ingredients are the *malunggay* and scallops. Kropeck, a well-loved crispy snack in the Philippines, is made of starches combined with either fish or shrimp extracts. The simple formulations and the product's taste make it ideal for replication, with a twist: incorporating healthier agricultural products without losing their cultural identity. Kropeck originated in our neighboring countries, Indonesia and Malaysia, as a deep-fried, crispy, traditional dish made with tapioca starch, mixed with vegetables and fish or shrimp. Over time, this product has become popular in Southeast Asia and beyond because of its crunchy texture and adaptable flavor⁽¹¹⁾. From tapioca starch as the main ingredient, the product evolved, and modern variations now include rice flour, sweet potatoes, and legumes, reflecting its efforts to improve its nutritional values⁽¹²⁾. Kropeck is also famous in Northern Iloilo, commonly available from bus stations to school canteens. Thus, the study believed that enhancing the main ingredients can improve local schoolchildren's health and support livelihood programs for parents.

Despite the growing interest in functional foods and marine-based nutrition, a significant gap exists in developing cheaper, locally sourced, and nutritionally fortified snacks tailored for learners. Furthermore, few studies have examined the balance between nutritional enhancement, product acceptability, and pricing feasibility for learners. Thereby contributing to the advancement of sustainable, healthy, and accessible snack innovations derived from local agricultural and marine resources. Thus, this study introduces an innovative kropeck formulation enriched with *malunggay* (*Moringa oleifera*) and scallop (*Pecten spp.*). The combination of *malunggay* and scallops will provide the nutritional strength of both land- and sea-based resources. Thus, the main objective is to develop and evaluate NutriKropeck, an innovative, marine-based, scallop-enriched kropeck, and to determine its potential as a functional, affordable, and nutritious marine-based snack for learners.

2 Methodology

This study employed an experimental research design to develop and evaluate Nutrikropeck, a functional marine-based snack formulated from *malunggay* (*Moringa oleifera*) powder and scallop meat. The procedure includes product formulation, sensory evaluation, nutritional analysis, pricing analysis, and validation procedures to ensure reliability and consistency of results.

2.1 Product Formulation and Development

Nutrikropeck was formulated using varying proportions of *malunggay* powder and scallop meat, combined with standard kropeck ingredients, including starch, seasoning, and binding agents. Several formulations were prepared to determine the most acceptable combination. Each formulation was prepared under standardized food preparation procedures to maintain consistency in ingredient measure, mixing, drying, and cooking conditions. Table 1 shows the ingredients of the product *malunggay*-scallop kropeck.

Table 1. Ingredients of *Malunggay*-Scallop Flavor Kropeck

Ingredients	TA	TB	TC	TD
Blended Scallops	600g	700g	800 g	900g
Cassava Starch	1000g	1100g	1200 g	1300g
Water	200ml	300ml	400 ml	500ml
Black Pepper	.5tbs	1tbs	2tbs	4tbs
Salt	2tsp	3tsp	4tsp	5tps
Garlic Powder	.5tbs	1tbs	2tsp	4tbs
Baking Powder	.5tbs	1tbs	2tsp	4tbs
Fresh Moringga	60g	80g	100g	150g

2.2 Gold-Standard Validation Procedures

To ensure the accuracy and credibility of the experimental results, the study followed gold-standard validation practices commonly used in food product research. However, the study’s purpose is only to assess the product’s acceptability. The nutritional and food composition analysis will be the next step of this study. In addition, measuring instruments such as weighing scales, thermometers, and moisture analyzers were calibrated prior to conducting the experiment to maintain measurement accuracy.

2.3 Respondents of the Study

The developed formulation was evaluated by a selected panel representing the target consumers. A purposive sample of respondents assessed the product on aroma, color, flavor, texture, and general acceptability using researcher-developed evaluation forms. Table 2 shows the number of respondents and their qualifications

Table 2. The Respondents of the Research Study

Respon- dents	Number of Respondents	Description
Parents	10	These are randomly selected from one public school in the district who are advocate of nutritional, safe, and affordable snacks for their children.
Faculty	10	These are teachers from elementary school and faculty from Hospitality Management at NISU, who are experts with experience in nutritional product development.
Local Vendors	10	The local vendors are those who sell from bus stations and school canteens, focusing on crackers.
Chdilren	5	The learners are those who like to eat kropecks but prefer foods that support academic performance.

2.4 Cost and Pricing Analysis

To ensure student-friendly pricing, the analysis was conducted based on the total production costs of the ingredients, processing, and packaging, plus an estimated market margin. The panelists decided on the final pricing to make it more affordable relative to typical snacks available in school environments.

2.5 Data Analysis

The sensory evaluation was analyzed using descriptive analysis, frequency count, percentages, mean, and standard deviation. For inferential analysis, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine significant differences in aroma, flavor, color, texture, and general acceptability. All statistical analyses were carried out using software, with a level of significance set at $p < 0.05$.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

To ensure the panelists' or evaluators' participation as consumers, no personal data was disclosed. Parent consent was required for learners' participation. The study was explained to the parents.

3 Results and Discussion

The results for aroma showed that Treatment A, with a mean score of 2.47, was interpreted as Less Acceptable. Treatment B and Treatment C have mean scores of 2.77 and 2.71, respectively, both rated Moderately Acceptable. And, Treatment D has 4.74, which was explained as Extremely Acceptable. The findings indicate that the ingredients in Treatment D are highly desirable among panelists as future consumers of the products. In addition, the combination of these two main ingredients produced a pleasant and appealing aroma that enhances the overall qualities of the local snack. Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for the four *malunggay*-scallop kropeck treatments based on aroma.

Treatment A was perceived as less desirable than other formulations. This may suggest that the proportions of ingredients used in Treatment A did not optimally meet the evaluators' sensory preferences. While Treatments B and C meet the evaluators' criteria, there is still room for improvement in aroma. The findings show that the formulations of these treatments are better than those of Treatment A. This suggests that the formulation provided aromas more aligned with the evaluators' preferences. In contrast, Treatment D had the highest mean, indicating that the formulation was highly preferred by the panelists. The results indicate that the proportion of the ingredients used produced the most desirable aroma. Thus, the findings represent the optimal formulation among treatments.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Four Treatments Based on Aroma

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Treatment A	35	2.49	0.74	Less Acceptable
Treatment B	35	2.77	0.81	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment C	35	2.71	0.71	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment D	35	4.74	0.61	Extremely Acceptable

The herbal, leafy scent of *malunggay* blended well with the mild, natural seafood aroma of the scallops, resulting in a well-balanced, inviting aroma. This balance makes the product appealing to a wide range of consumers who seek a nutritional snack without compromising aroma⁽¹³⁾. The achievement of the right balance between *malunggay* and scallop in terms of pleasant aroma makes consumers interested in local snacks made from locally available, nutrient-rich ingredients⁽¹⁴⁾. A study on jelly candy enhanced with powdered moringa leaves found that the category aroma received 68% approval and was interpreted as good⁽¹⁵⁾. One study found that naturally dried scallops have a distinct fishy odor⁽¹⁶⁾. Thus, the fresh, earthy aroma of powdered *malunggay* and the blended, fresh meat of scallops play an important role in this process, producing a desirable scent.

A study on the aromas of flavored delicacies such as leche flan, *kutsinta*, and pancakes flavored with *malunggay* showed significant results. The rater, especially the teachers, gave perfect scores because the *malunggay*-flavored delicacies were very acceptable⁽¹⁷⁾. Like the study on scallop kropeck, the findings were also very acceptable to the evaluators⁽¹⁰⁾. As a result, combining the two ingredients, the kropeck enhanced with *malunggay* and scallop has potential in the markets in terms of aroma.

Table 4 presents descriptive statistics for the four treatments by color. The color results showed that Treatments A, B, C, and D had mean scores of 2.54, 2.63, 2.60, and 4.83, respectively, and were rated as Less Acceptable, Moderately Acceptable, Less

Acceptable, and Extremely Acceptable, respectively. The sensory evaluation results for color showed variations in acceptability among the treatments. Neither Treatment A nor Treatment C’s formulation was highly preferred by the panelists, and the appearance was less appealing due to variations in ingredients and processing conditions, resulting in a color that did not closely match the expected product appearance. In contrast, Treatment B was rated acceptable by the panelists, although it was not the most preferred by the evaluators. But more visually appealing compared to Treatments A and C, but still lacked the optimal appearance desired by the panelists. Compared to Treatment D, the results indicate that the panelists strongly preferred the colors of this formulation. The results suggest that Treatment D exhibited a more attractive, desirable color, which may have been influenced by balanced formulations and appropriate processing, both of which enhanced the product’s visual quality.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistical Analysis of the Four Treatments in Terms of Color

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Treatment A	35	2.54	1.12	Less Acceptable
Treatment B	35	2.63	1.09	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment C	35	2.60	1.14	Less Acceptable
Treatment D	35	4.83	0.45	Extremely Acceptable

This demonstrated that Treatment D has a pleasant and catchy light green color, which is the usual color of local Kroepeck. *Malunggay* imparts a greenish color when added to the product⁽⁴⁾. The color of the *malunggay* becomes more distinctive as the blended scallops become whiter, especially as the measurements of the herbal product increase across different treatments. But the darker strips come from other parts of the scallop and other ingredients, which add to the contrast and visual depth. This makes the Kroepeck more visually appealing and appetizing to the consumers⁽¹⁸⁾. Additionally, color is always associated with freshness and quality; the evaluators’ favorable rating highlights the importance of visual appeal in food production⁽⁴⁾.

Table 5 presents descriptive statistics for the four treatments by flavor. The findings indicate that both Treatment A and Treatment B were rated Moderately Acceptable, with mean scores of 2.86 and 2.94, respectively. Treatment C was labeled as Less Acceptable, with the lowest mean scores of 2.74. Treatment D has an almost-perfect score of 4.94 and is rated as Extremely Acceptable. Treatments A and B denote that the panelists generally found the flavor of these formulations satisfactory, but they may not have fully met their preferences compared to the most favored formulation. This recommends that Treatments A and B produced a flavor that was generally pleasing but still had room for improvement. Treatment C suggests that the flavor was not well preferred by the panelists. This suggests that the proportion of ingredients used may have resulted in a flavor that was either too strong, too bland, or less balanced than in the other treatments. Treatment D was strongly preferred by the panelists because it suggested a more balanced formulation, which greatly contributed to its higher acceptability.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistical Analysis of the Four Treatments in terms of Flavors

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Treatment A	35	2.86	0.97	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment B	35	2.94	0.91	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment C	35	2.74	0.95	Less Acceptable
Treatment D	35	4.94	0.17	Extremely Acceptable

The bitter taste of *malunggay* mellows, blending well with the scallop’s sweetness and savory meatiness, resulting in a favorable, enjoyable flavor profile for the kroepeck. This mixture allows the local product to taste palatable without being overwhelming⁽¹⁹⁾. Adding powdered *malunggay* to the ingredients gives an herbal flavor⁽⁴⁾ to the kroepeck. According to the panelists, Banisil crackers enhanced with *malunggay* were pleasant in taste⁽²⁰⁾. Regarding scallop kroepeck, one study found that evaluators rated the product as very acceptable⁽¹⁰⁾. *Malunggay* nutrients are used in many food products today.

Table 6 presents descriptive statistics for the four treatments regarding texture. Both Treatment A and Treatment B had the lowest mean scores of 2.20 and 2.46, respectively, and were classified as Less Acceptable. Treatment C has a mean score of 2.63 and is explained as Moderately Acceptable. As with other categories, Treatment D again had the highest mean score of 4.89 and was rated Extremely Acceptable. This indicates that the evaluators highly appreciated the *malunggay*-scallop kroepeck’s texture, which was due to its crispiness and overall mouthfeel.

Treatments A and B indicate that the panelists were less satisfied with the texture of these formulations because the consistency, crispness, and mouthfeel may not have met expectations, due to variations in ingredient proportions and processing conditions. Treatments C, according to the panelists, have consistency and mouthfeel but still require improvements to achieve the desirable texture that could further enhance consumer preference. Treatment D was the panelists’ strong preference for

Table 6. Descriptive Statistical Analysis of the Four Treatments in terms of Texture

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Treatment A	35	2.20	0.90	Less Acceptable
Treatment B	35	2.46	1.01	Less Acceptable
Treatment C	35	2.63	1.03	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment D	35	4.89	0.31	Extremely Acceptable

texture because the formulation has balanced ingredients and appropriate processing, resulting in a pleasing consistency and mouthfeel. Texture is always a key feature in kropeck. Light, crunchy bites are always important to consumers. One study showed that crispiness makes eating snacks like kropeck enjoyable to bite and easy to chew⁽⁴⁾. The mixtures of *malunggay* and scallops didn't compromise the structure of kropeck. The traditional appeal remains, enhancing the textures of the two main ingredients and meeting consumer expectations. Thus, this supports its potential as market-ready, useful snacks⁽²¹⁾. Thus, this NutriKropeck has the potential to be available in the market with further studies.

Table 7 presents a descriptive analysis of the four treatments regarding acceptability. In terms of general acceptability, Treatment A has a mean score of 2.49 and is explained as Less Acceptable. Treatment B and Treatment C have mean scores of 2.69 and 2.71, respectively, and are rated Moderately Acceptable. Treatment D's mean score was 4.91 and construed as Extremely Acceptable. This suggests that Treatment D was appealing across all categories.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistical Analysis of the Four Treatments in Term of General Acceptability

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Treatment A	35	2.49	0.74	Less Acceptable
Treatment B	35	2.69	0.2	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment C	35	2.71	0.75	Moderately Acceptable
Treatment D	35	4.91	0.28	Extremely Acceptable

Treatment A indicates that the overall quality of the formulation was not highly preferred; Treatments B and C show that the formulation was satisfactory; and Treatment D was the most preferred by the panelists. Just like the study on different local delicacies such as leche flan, *kutsinta*, and pancakes flavored with *malunggay*, the general acceptability was very high, but ratings varied because they depend on factors such as evaluators' preferences and attitudes⁽¹⁷⁾.

Table 8 presents the inferential results for the *malunggay*-scallop kropeck on aroma, color, flavor, texture, and general acceptability.

Table 8. The Inferential Statistics of the *Malunggay*-Scallop Kropecks in different Sensory Evaluations

	Aroma	Color	Flavor	Texture	General Acceptability
N	35	35	35	35	35
Chi-Square	79.69	76.76	71.07	83.21	81.16
Df	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Across all identified categories of this innovation, there were no significant differences among the four treatments. This means that changing the ratios of *malunggay* and scallops did not greatly affect how the panelists perceived the products in terms of the sensory qualities. These strong results showed that the product was well-liked across all sensory attributes. The study of scallop kropecks with three treatments showed that all were viable. Despite changes in ingredient amounts, the sensory attributes remained unchanged. With this, all the treatments have potential for markets, with only minor changes required for development and commercialization⁽¹⁰⁾. Furthermore, a study on *malunggay* and *alugbati* for kropeck found that the amount of the ingredients applied can significantly affect the quality of the products as perceived by consumers⁽²²⁾. Thus, vegetables and other agricultural products are now in demand as main ingredients for NutriKropeck.

Figure 1 shows the responses of the 35 panelists to the three proposed logos for this product.

Logo 1 got 15% responses; Logo 2 was 11%; and Logo 3, with the highest score of 74%, was Logo 3. A logo is important for products, but how these patterns are presented also affects consumers' decisions. Just like the study about the diagonal and vertical appearance of logos' impact on consumers showed that a diagonal-oriented logo leads to more favorable attitudes

Fig 1. The responses of the Panelists on the 3 Proposed Logos

towards the product⁽²³⁾. Also, colors significantly affect consumers’ perceptions of food products. Thus, one study showed that red as the primary color is preferred, and logos with names are also favored⁽²⁴⁾. However, in this study, the colors used are the natural colors of *malunggay* and scallops: green, yellow, and a little red. Figure 2 shows the logos preferred by the evaluators. The logo featured a fresh, open scallop from a shell.

Fig 2. The Preferred Logo of the Panelists

Consumers tend to prefer products with simple, flat logos. Thus, brand logo designs are likely to impact food intake. With these findings, the selected logo has great potential to resonate with local consumers, who will love the proposed *malunggay*-scallop kropeck, as well as its beneficial health effects for children in Northern Iloilo, Philippines.

Figure 3 shows the proposed pricing of the products. The price proposal is based on the target consumer, learners from Northern Iloilo, Philippines, who need nutritional snacks to study well and achieve high grades.

Fig 3. Proposed Product Pricing Based on Weight

A study on local delicacies in Biliran, Philippines, found that maintaining a good value-for-money ratio to boost customer delight is an essential factor. This can also contribute to the long-term success of the local delicacies⁽²⁵⁾. Pricing is important for customers to patronize products. A well-structured pricing model enhances customer satisfaction⁽²⁶⁾. Thus, the researchers agreed with the panelists' pricing selections. The product is affordable but with nutritional values that help learners in the Philippines. The price is also like the local kropeck product.

4 Conclusion

This study developed an innovative marine-based snack product by combining *malunggay* (*Moringa oleifera*), a nutrient-rich agricultural crop, with scallop, a locally available marine resource, to produce NutriKropeck. The results of the sensory evaluation in terms of aroma, color, taste, texture, and general acceptability showed that Treatment D consistently obtained the highest mean scores across all sensory attributes, with evaluators describe as "Extremely Acceptable." In contrast, Treatments A, B, and C received lower ratings from less acceptable to moderately acceptable, indicating that the formulation used in Treatment D provided the preferred balance of ingredients without compromising product quality. The findings demonstrate that incorporating *malunggay* and scallop as main ingredients in the production of NutriKropeck is a promising food innovation. The product has potential nutritional benefits for learners in the basic education curriculum. Moreover, the proposed product pricing is affordable and accessible for consumers, even with the addition of scallops, which are sometimes considered premium seafood ingredients. The product branding and packaging are simple yet appealing, indicating potential marketability and consumer interest. Despite the positive responses to the sensory attributes, further study is recommended. The study recognizes the need to scientifically validate the product's nutritional claims. Additionally, shelf-life testing, food safety evaluation, and packaging studies should be conducted with the help of the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) and other relevant institutions. Furthermore, support for sustainable development, the commercialization of the product, and multi-sector collaboration is recommended. These agencies include the Department of Agriculture (DA), Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), DOST, DepEd, and local government units (LGUs). These institutions may provide technical support, nutritional testing, livelihood training, and funding for equipment and small-scale

production facilities. Furthermore, initiatives such as community-based *malunggay* planting, backyard gardening promotion, and sustainable management of scallop resources are encouraged to ensure a stable supply of raw materials. Protecting scallop production areas will also contribute to the long-term sustainability of marine resources and local fisheries' livelihoods. Finally, future research conducted by the NISU community and external experts is required to further validate the nutritional values, economic viability, and health benefits of *malunggay*-scallop kropecks. Through expanded studies and interdisciplinary collaboration, this food innovation has the potential to contribute to food security, community livelihood, and the promotion of locally sourced functional food products in the Philippines.

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7 Conflict of Interest

The author has declared no conflict of interest.

8 Authors Contribution

Fernan Peniero Tupas: Conceptualization; Methodology; Funding acquisition; Formal analysis; Statistical analysis; Project administration; Writing—original draft; Writing—review & editing; Validation; Visualization of the logo and packaging.

Matt Numer B. Ofalla: Writing the original draft; review & editing; Project administration.

Portia B. Sta. Ana: Methodology; Resources; Data validation.

John Paul Longno: Validation; Investigation; review & editing (instruments and research materials).

Mhar A. Palina: Methodology; Formal analysis; review & editing of the manuscript.

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